

REFLECTION OF ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS IN THE SANSKRIT TEXT

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Abstract: Environment plays a very significant role in human civilization. Human beings have close relations with the biosphere in which they live. The whole environment and ecology consisting of earth, air, water, plants and animals provide the necessary and sufficient conditions for sustaining life. The aim and objective of this study is to showcase the Sanskrit text of talking care of the environment. Sanskrit literature is not only rich in the grammatical composition and romantic expression but also in knowledge about environment, its destruction and the needs for its protection which comes up with many contexts every now and then whenever any attempt is made to study this literature. Starting from the Vedic age till now it carries a number of appearances in the writings of scholars. This need to be explored in detail as the vast size and span of it leaves enough scope for researchers to dig up those of knowledge. In this paper different sources of knowledge are studied to find out the concern and knowledge on environment and its protection. It includes all those valuable sources to do maximum justice to the objective of the paper.

Keywords: Sanskrit texts, environment and protection.

The increasing rate of industrialization in this era of globalization it has become an urgent need to protect the environment. As a result of this, enormous movements and conferences on this topic have been organized just to make people sense their responsibility in this regard. Revisiting Sanskrit texts will be a great decision in this matter which is the reservoir of knowledge about environment and steps for its protection. For ex- the four Vedas, sixteen *Upanisads*, eighteen *Purāṇas*, two Epics and many other Sanskrit texts possess a great treasure on the importance of environment and its protection.

The present paper is an attempt to revisit the Sanskrit texts and explore the references regarding the protection of environment. The main objectives of this paper are as follows:

1. To revisit the Sanskrit texts.
2. To explore the references of environment and its protection in the Sanskrit texts.
3. To understand the relevance of those references in the context of present time.

Reference of Environment and need of its protection in the Vedas:

There is hardly any sector of knowledge got untouched in the Vedas. The Vedas are the great source of knowledge. There can be found several references to environment and its importance in the Vedas. It covers the matters like environmental balance, water and rainfall, weather and many others related to environment. As per the Vedas there are five elements that the world is consisted of. These are- Earth, Water, Fire, Air and Space. These are known as *Pancamahābhuta*. People understood about the importance of preserving environment that time too. They tried to think over precautions for preserving the environment. During the Vedic era, the deities worshipped by the common folk are part of Mother Nature. For ex- *Surya*, *Agni*, *Prithvi*, *Varuna*, *Indra* and many other who are responsible for smooth running of the eco

system. Despite this each Veda gives some knowledge like- Rig Veda teaches us that “Thousands and hundreds of years if you want to enjoy the fruits and happiness in life, then take- up systematic planting of trees.” *Atharvaveda* teaches “let there be peace in heaven, the earth, the atmosphere, the water, the herbs, the vegetation, among the divine beings and in *Brāhmaṇa*, the absolute reality. Let everything be in peace and in peace”. *Atharvaveda* teaches us about the importance of domestic animals at home.

Reference of Environment in the Purānas:

Like the *Upanisad* and the Vedas, the Puranas are too filled with several messages in favour of saving the environment. Here the provision of Idol worship can be found. The *Puranas* mention about the worship of the Idols along with their *Vāhanas*. *Vāhanas* are again chosen very carefully keeping in mind about their importance. For ex- for Goddess Lakshmi, owl is chosen as vahana because of its importance in paddy fields by protecting the grains from the insects. Another reason for selecting owl as the vahana of Goddess Lakshmi is to protect it from getting extinction. On the other hand, for Goddess *Saraswati*, Swan is chosen very carefully because of its expertise in finding out the right object out of all. For instance, if a mixture of water and milk is provided then a swan can easily consume milk from the mixture which reveals its excellence. The *Kālikā Purāna* mentions about the process of worshipping Mother Durga. The use of nine leaves i.e banana leaf, pomegranate leaf, turmeric leaf, Jayanti leaf, Bel leaf, Asoka leaf, Arum leaf, Cola Cassia leaf and Rice leaf in Durga puja signifies the importance of these plants in our life. In the *Skandapurāna*, reference to the importance of *Tulsi* and *Amla* are found. All these above- mentioned leaves carry some medicinal elements in them because of which these plants should be preserved.

Reference of Environment in the Epics:

The two great epics- The *Mahābhārata* and The *Ramayana* are great source of lessons on environment. In the *Ramayana*, *Valmiki* stands in favour of protecting the animals and plants. The king Rama too is found showing affection towards environment. In the *Aranyakānda* of the *Ramayana*, the king Rama is found adoring the whole nature while entering his newly constructed cottage.

The *Mahabharata* also teaches a lot about the importance of nature. The *Brahmāstra* is the most powerful weapon of all. When *Aswatthamā* in the war between the *Kauravas* and the *Pāndavas* was left with the only weapon, the *Brahmāstra* to fight against Arjuna, then he was repeatedly alarmed from the heaven about its devastating outcome i.e death of *Arjuna* and destruction of the whole world. This shows how people were concerned about the nature at that time.

Reference of Environment in the *Arthasāstra* written by *Kauṭilya*:

Though the text *Arthasāstra* is basically known for its concentration on politics but there can be found some references relating to the preservation of the environment. Prohibition is made in selling the flesh of animals, unauthorized killing of any animal is banned, construction of slaughter houses are restricted are some holy provisions circulated by the *Arthasāstra*. A designation is also made to look after such matters by the title ‘*Sunadhyaksa*’. *Sunadhyaksa* has been given the full liberty to impose any severe punishment, impose high rate of fine if he or she observes any unauthorized action against the plants and animals.

Reference of Environment in the Sanskrit dramas:

Famous drama, *Kālidās's Abhijnanaśakuntalam* is an excellent example to refer about the presence of love towards nature in ancient era. Through the character, *Śakuntala*, *Kālidāsa* teaches the global readers about the significance of nature. Imposition of strict rules in the hermitage regarding killing of animals even for the king too shows the great importance of nature. Through the love tale of *Śakuntala* and *Dushyant*, *Kālidāsa* shows his love for nature and need for preserving the environment in the drama.

Sriharsa's Nagananda, composed in the 7th century too reflects on the concept of preservation of plants and animals. Here the prince *Jimutavahana* sacrifices his life for a serpent in this drama. Garuda, the king of birds continued to kill all the serpents and the king of Serpent attempted his best to make Garuda understand about the importance of serpents for the nature. The reference of a special heavenly tree of wishes, '*Kalpataru*' reveals importance of nature for the living creatures.

Conclusion:

The study of the texts written in Sanskrit guides people to save environment. The study highlights the conservation and preservation of the environment. All the texts more or less possess some references for the preservation of our environment and can be taken as guiding source whenever people feel the need of it. Revisiting such valuable texts is the smartest way before taking any decision regarding the nature and promoting any provision on environment.

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